

Public security and artificial intelligence: new paradigms¹

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Abstract: The object of study of this paper is to address the issue of the conditions and possibilities of public security policies with the use of artificial intelligence and information technologies, taking into account fundamental individual and social rights and guarantees demarcated by the democratic rule of law, particularly in Brazil. The hypothesis and proposal for addressing these issues is based on the establishment of clear regulatory frameworks and guarantee policies by the State, from which such policies can be instituted and developed, with permanent internal and external control, notably social control.

Keywords: Public security; public policies; fundamental rights; rule of law; control of public policies.

Resumo: O objeto de estudo do presente trabalho é enfrentar a problemática das condições e possibilidades de políticas públicas de segurança com o uso de inteligência artificial e tecnologias de informação, levando em conta direitos e garantias fundamentais individuais e sociais demarcadas pelo Estado democrático de direito, nomeadamente no Brasil. A hipótese e proposta de enfrentamento destas questões se dá a partir do estabelecimento de marcos normativos claros e políticas de garantias por parte do Estado, a partir do que tais políticas podem se instituir e desenvolver, com permanente controle interno e externo, notadamente social.

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Palavras-chave: Segurança pública; políticas públicas; direitos fundamentais; Estado de direito; controle de políticas públicas.

Summary: 1 Introductory notes – 2 Knowledge society vs. surveillance society – 3 Reactions to the surveillance society: perspectives – 4 Concluding notes – References

1 Introductory notes

It is undeniable that, in all areas of life, artificial intelligence (AI) has become increasingly present and functional, facilitating everyday tasks.¹ Due to its sophistication and technological optimization, it can easily be perceived as a tool that is free of errors, without prejudices and stereotypes, characteristics commonly associated with human beings. However, if we live in a society in which everything we (re)produce is influenced by historical, cultural, and social factors, why would AIs—created by humans—not also replicate stigmas related to class, race, gender, ethnicity, among others?²

The *algorithmization of life*,³ which is present in social media and *streaming services* and has gained ground in countless fields, has increasingly influenced public security policies. Despite this, problems of discrimination and structural prejudice in certain policies of this nature remain the same, and the discriminatory and prejudiced use of AI cannot remove the responsibility of the State at this point (because, if there was an error, it was the fault of the algorithm, not the programmer).⁴ It is interesting to note this parallel: on the one hand, technology is presented as a solution, but at the same time, civil society at different moments will contest that.

¹ A clear example is the use of artificial intelligence in judicial and administrative decision-making: VALLE, Vivian Lima López; FUENTES I GASÓ, Josep Ramón; AJUS, Atílio Martins. Judicial decision-making assisted by artificial intelligence and the Victor System of the Federal Supreme Court. *Journal of Constitutional Research*, Curitiba, v. 10, n. 2, e252, May/Aug. 2023. DOI: 10.5380/rinc.v10i2.92598; BITENCOURT, Caroline Müller; MARTINS, Luisa Helena Nicknig. Artificial intelligence in the constitutional bodies responsible for auditing the Brazilian public administration. *Journal of Constitutional Research*, Curitiba, v. 10, n. 3, e253, Sept./Dec. 2023. DOI: 10.5380/rinc.v10i3.93650; TOLEDO, Claudia; PESSOA, Daniel. The use of artificial intelligence in judicial decision-making. *Journal of Constitutional Research*, Curitiba, v. 10, n. 1, e237, Jan./Apr. 2023. DOI: 10.5380/rinc.v10i1.86319; SIERRA CADENA, Grenfieth de Jesus. Implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the High Courts of Colombia: the cases of the Constitutional Court and the Council of State. *Euro-Latin American Journal of Administrative Law*, Santa Fe, v. 11, n. 1, e253, Jan./July 2024. DOI 10.14409/redoeda.v11i1.13824.

² SÁNCHEZ DÍAZ, María Fernanda. The Impact of Generative Artificial Intelligence on Human Rights. *Euro-Latin American Journal of Administrative Law*, Santa Fe, v. 11, n. 1, e252, Jan./June 2024. DOI: 10.14409/redoeda.v11i1.13612.

³ PUSCHEL, André Felipe Silva; RODRIGUES, Roberto Tassis; VALLE, Vivian Cristina Lima López. The ethical dilemma of algorithmic decision-making in public administration. *A&C – Revista de Direito Administrativo & Constitucional*, Belo Horizonte, year 22, no. 90, pp. 207-226, Oct./Dec. 2022. DOI: 10.21056/aec.v22i90.1737.

⁴RUARO, Regina Linden; RODRIGUEZ, Daniel Piñeiro. Personal data protection and State surveillance: the risks of digital discrimination and the Federal Supreme Court's vision. *A&C – Revista de Direito Administrativo & Constitucional*, Belo Horizonte, year 22, no. 90, pp. 63–85, Oct./Dec. 2022. DOI: 10.21056/aec.v22i90.1658.

This paper aims to address these scenarios and their risks, as well as initiatives to control them. To this end, we have chosen the following specific objectives: (i) to demarcate the relationships between the knowledge society and the surveillance society; (ii) institutional and political reactions to the surveillance society; (iii) to propose premises that enable democratic public security policies for the use of new technologies with the use of AI in the field of public security. We intend to use the deductive method in this work, testing our hypotheses with the foundations that will be outlined below. To this end, we will use a research technique with indirect documentation, namely bibliographic.

2 Knowledge society vs. surveillance society

The term "information society" has been incorporated in recent years into global political, academic, and media discourse. Manuel Castells argues that this society is a new technological, economic, and social system; an economy in which productivity growth does not depend on quantitative increases in production factors (capital, labor, natural resources), but on the application of knowledge and information in management, production, and distribution, both in processes and products.

These societies are characterized by being based on knowledge and efforts to convert information into knowledge. The greater the amount of information generated by a society, the greater the need to convert it into knowledge.

One aspect of particular relevance in the development of "information and knowledge societies" is the *speed* with which information is generated, transmitted, and processed. Today, information can be obtained almost instantaneously and often from the same source that produces it, transcending borders and limitations of space and time.

Although there are various interpretations of the scope and meaning of the concept of this society, what is certain is that it reconfigures the ways in which all people carry out most of their activities, based on new ways of undertaking and performing everyday actions; therefore, we can say that it is also a synthesis of structural paradigm shifts in multiple fields of life.⁶

⁵ CASTELS, Manuel. *The Network Society: The Information Age. Economy, Society, and Culture*. Madrid: Alianza Editorial, 1997. v. 1. p. 67.

⁶ We discuss this in greater depth in the book LEAL, Rogerio Gesta. *Public security in the democratic rule of law – Advances and setbacks*. São Paulo: Tirant lo Blanch, 2023.

In the early 1980s, Alvin Toffler anticipated with remarkable clarity the advent of the information society, recalling that, more than 10,000 years ago, the first wave introduced important changes in history, driven by the agricultural revolution, transforming the living conditions of primitive hunters and gatherers, who formed peasant societies in which productivity depended mainly on the demonstration of human and animal strength, as well as the sun, wind, and water. The beneficiaries of this transformation were those who understood that the new organization would be focused on the countryside.⁷

With the second wave, the industrial revolution triggered profound changes in history,⁸ giving rise to a new civilization centered on industry and large-scale production. Productivity depended on the relationship that man established with machines. Those who did not understand the meaning and scope of the rationality imposed by the new order were left behind, significantly limited in their production capabilities.

The third wave, in turn, introduces a new society based on information, knowledge, and creativity. In these societies, productivity depends on the development of new technologies, which, according to Toffler, would allow man to do less and think more. In other words, the development of advanced information and communication technologies allows for the configuration of a new social space, as a third environment, marked by unprecedented models of markets, cultures, and perceptions of the world.⁹

It was imagined that, in this new world of infinite possibilities for knowledge/enlightenment, human rationality would reach a level of excellence that would enable human life and relationships to develop in a more civilized and sustainable way, with harmony, social justice, and *security*. What a mistake!

An unprecedented *paradigm shift in the collapse* of this knowledge/information society: the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001, on the Twin Towers in New York (USA) ushered in what we might call the fourth wave of civilization: the Panoptic Era of the Surveillance Society.

When we imagined that the new technologies generated by the information society could ensure the prevention of problems of the most diverse kinds, they have proved powerless in the face of continuous emergencies, risks, and dangers that are currently being created across the globe.

⁷ TOFFLER, Alvin. *The Third Wave*. Mexico: Edivisión, 1981. p. 81.

⁸ MARTNEZ GARBIRAS, María Margarita; SÁNCHEZ-HUERTAS, Luis Fernando. The shortcuts from the Fourth Industrial Revolution to democracy: a reflection on lessons learned from Lafont and Berlin. *A&C – Revista de Direito Administrativo & Constitucional*, Belo Horizonte, year 23, no. 94, pp. 43-62, Oct./Dec. 2023. DOI: 10.21056/aec.v23i94.1725.

⁹ In this sense, DAVARRA RODRIGUEZ, Miguel Angel. *From information highways to virtual society*. Madrid: Aranzadi Editorial, 2008. p. 51 et seq.

caused by acts of terrorism and immense violence, as well as by environmental, consumption, energy, racial, ethnic, biological, and criminal factors, among others, proving that the belief that, through knowledge and technological innovations, we would free ourselves from any fears, cease to be creatures, and become creators of the community in which we live is illusory.¹⁰ In other words, fears and uncertainties, as

Mongardini points out, continue becoming increasingly characteristic features of our daily lives,¹¹ and all it took was a microscopic virus, the generator of Covid-19,¹² for us to find ourselves alone and desperate once again! Suddenly we are back in the days of the terrible Spanish flu, with the same masks, the same fears, but above all the same mistakes, such as not revealing the spread of the disease to society at the right time; or, worse still, communicating manipulated and often even false news—particularly through virtual social networks, precisely those that could greatly help in the tragic scenarios we are experiencing.

¹⁰ See the excellent text by HARARI, Yuval Noah. *Homo Deus. A Brief History of Tomorrow*. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras, 2016. See also the text by DOMINICI, Piero. *La società dell'irresponsabilità*. Milan: Franco Angeli, 2015. p. 28 et seq.

¹¹ MONGARDINI, Carlo. *Le dimensioni sociali della paura*. Milan: Franco Angeli, 2010. p. 46. Along the same lines, see the excellent text by ZOLO, Danilo. *Sula paura – Fragilità, aggressività, potere*. Milan: Feltrinelli Editore, 2011. p. 49 ff. In this text, the author asks himself: "Why did fear so often make me aggressive, and why were my aggression and the arrogance of others so closely intertwined? I wondered, in essence, what was the relationship between fear, aggression, and the violence unleashed by my fellow human beings over the millennia" (p. 11). It is important to discuss these issues because, as the author points out, recalling Arnold Gehlen: "With great skill, we have pushed death out of our field of vision. Death plays behind white lacquered doors."

¹² On the legal impacts of COVID-19 on human rights and administrative law, see: CASTILLO ARJONA, Mónica. The COVID-19 phenomenon and its social effects on 21st-century administrative law.

XXI. Euro-Latin American Journal of Administrative Law, Santa Fe, v. 8, n. 1, p. 173-187, Jan./June 2021. DOI: 10.14409/reoeda.v8i1.9548; SÁNCHEZ DIAZ, Maria Fernanda; ROMERO TELLO, Ana Guadalupe. Covid-19, Human Rights, and the State in the Face of the Pandemic. *Euro-Latin American Journal of Administrative Law*, Santa Fe, v. 8, n. 1, p. 233-254, Jan./June 2021. DOI: 10.14409/reoeda.v8i1.9525; HERNANDES, Luiz Eduardo Camargo Outeiro; PIOVESAN, Flávia. Judicial challenges in times of pandemic: strengthening dialogue between the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights and the Brazilian Supreme Court for the protection of human rights. *Journal of Constitutional Research*, Curitiba, v. 9, n. 2, p. 371-388, May/Aug. 2022. DOI: 10.5380/rinc.v9i2.86138; NÓBREGA, Marcos; HEINEN, Juliano. The forces that will change Public Administration post-Covid: transparency 2.0, blockchain, and smart contracts. *A&C – Journal of Administrative & Constitutional Law*, Belo Horizonte, year 21, no. 85, pp. 217-230, July/Sept. 2021. DOI: 10.21056/aec.v21i85.1405; RODRÍGUEZ-ARANA MUÑOZ, Jaime.

Administrative Law and human dignity (on the post-pandemic reconstruction of Administrative Law). *A&C – Revista de Direito Administrativo & Constitucional*, Belo Horizonte, year 22, no. 88, pp. 11-33, Apr./Jun. 2022. DOI: 10.21056/aec.v22i88.1646; BOMTEMPO, Eugênio Moraes; CARMONA, Paulo Cavichioli. Social solidarity in the Covid-19 pandemic. *A&C – Administrative & Constitutional Law Journal*, Belo Horizonte, year 22, no. 89, pp. 251-276, July/Sept. 2022. DOI: 10.21056/aec.v22i89.1662.

¹³The *Spanish flu* was caused by an influenza virus that spread around the world between 1918 and 1919. Its origin is unknown, and it caused the deaths of around 50 million people, with some statistics suggesting up to 100 million deaths, according to data collected on *the website*: <https://www.historiadomundo.com.br/idade-contemporanea/gripe-espanhola.htm>. Accessed on: Mar. 22, 2023.

¹⁴ VALLE, Vivian Cristina Lima López; RUIZ, Maria Guadalupe Fernandes; BÜTTNER, Marcielly. Fake news, influence on the formation of public opinion and impacts on the legitimacy of public decision-making. *A&C – Revista de Direito Administrativo & Constitucional*, Belo Horizonte, year 24, no. 95, pp. 73-97, Jan./Mar. 2024. DOI: 10.21056/aec.v24i95.1898.

These facts have shown us how the social construction of the risks and dangers that surround us (understood as socially constructed attributes) has provided solid theoretical and empirical bases for the design of often authoritarian policies (including public security). This is why authors such as Ferrajoli insist on the thesis that neoconstitutionalism, in order to rise to these new challenges, must build guarantees capable of creating rational and credible alternatives to predictions of a future characterized by uncertainty, violence, inequality, and environmental devastation.

Even though contemporary constitutions have sought to create instruments for crisis management, it is necessary to constantly reflect on the possible paradox of democratic regimes that manage to destroy themselves by using processes and procedures (which they themselves created) in an undemocratic manner. As D'Agostini and Ferrera tell us, in times of crisis it is easy to overestimate the need for security and underestimate the value of freedom; and this is because, without security, there is no freedom. But it is also true that today's constitutional history clearly shows us how the breakdown of the protection of rights and freedoms in the name of defending security has been present for a long time.

For this reason, we can say that security, as a multifaceted and polysemic constitutional good, can occur in a material and ideal sense; objective and subjective; individual and collective; internal and external, increasingly and routinely subject to judgments of weighting against other interests of constitutional importance, even beyond traditional emergency environments. As Walzer tells us, without security, no form of political representation based on consensus is possible; and freedom, here, appears as that peace of mind that comes from the conviction of being safe.

For all these reasons, prevention and precaution have become, in the present day, the *règles de droit* par excellence, the mantra of all public policies:

¹⁵ FERRAJOLI, Luigi. *Democracy through rights*. Rome: Laterza, 2013. p. 27.

¹⁶ D'AGOSTINI, Franca; FERRERA, Maurizio. *The truths of power – Six aleatory rights*. Rome: Einaudi, 2019. p. 81. In truth, history has already taught us that behind the apparent rule of law there are always men who govern and legislate, which is why every legal norm is destined to formalize the will/desires and choices of power.

¹⁷ On this point, see the excellent text by COLE, David. *Enemy Aliens – double standards and constitutional freedoms in the war on terrorism*. New York: The New Press, 2003. p. 77. Similarly, see the book by CERI, Paolo. *La società vulnerabile – Quale sicurezza, quale libertà*. Rome/Bari: Laterza, 2003. p. 38 ff.

¹⁸ WALZER, Michael. *Freedom and its enemies in the age of the war on terrorism*. Rome/Bari: Laterza, 2010. p. 43.

¹⁹ As in VERHOEVEN, Charles Leben. *Le principe de précaution – Aspects de droit international et communautaire*. Paris: Éditions Panthéon-Assas, 2022. p. 41. The author reminds us that the precautionary principle comes into play when it is appropriate to take appropriate measures, even in the face of risks that have not been fully scientifically proven, thus differing from the prevention principle, which, however, operates when scientific information about the danger and harmfulness is certain, consistent, and conclusive.

concerned with minimizing risks, dangers, and fears that may prevail over other rights, and shaping the actions of public administration as a whole. And in the name of all this, global public policies—physical and virtual—have been created for maximum security against known and unknown risks and dangers, even if this is to the detriment of some hard-won fundamental individual rights and guarantees, such as privacy and intimacy.

Let us remember that it was under the pretext of its crusade against international terrorism that the Bush administration promoted, after September 11, 2001, legislative initiatives that imposed significant restrictions on freedom of expression and rights related to personal privacy, including: the Wiretap Act, the Electronic Communications Privacy Act, Computer Fraud and Abuse Act, Foreign Intelligence Surveillance Act, Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act, Money Laundering Act, Immigration and Nationality Act, Bank Secrecy Act, Financial Privacy Act, USA Patriot Act, and Anti-Terrorism Act of 2001.²⁰

In order to exercise effective panoptic control over information circulating on the internet, President Bush's administration promoted the adaptation of the aforementioned regulatory framework, namely through the *USA Patriot Act*, granting broad powers to government security agencies to monitor information circulating on the internet and authorizing them to intercept all communications they deemed "suspicious."²¹ Alongside this, it also created the CAPPs II (*Computer Assisted Passenger Pre-Screening*) program. This system draws on information that airlines store in their passenger records and includes data on trips taken, as well as possible criminal records and unspecified information. On the other hand, AI tools and new technologies for accessing, collecting, and managing information can be enablers of democratic spaces, but they can also be authoritarian. We need only look at the regimes in Iran and China, which use them to suppress freedom of expression, improve surveillance techniques, disseminate cutting-edge propaganda, and pacify their populations with entertainment.

²⁰ "Wiretap Statute, Electronic Communications Privacy Act, Computer Fraud and Abuse Act, Foreign Intelligence Surveillance Act, Family Education Rights and Privacy Act, Money Laundering Act, Immigration and Nationality Act, Bank Secrecy Act, Right to Financial Privacy Act, USA Patriotic Act, Anti-Terrorism Act 2001" – according to information from *the website*: <https://epic.org/privacy/terrorism/usapatriot/>. Accessed on: April 27, 2024.

²¹ We now know that the internet can, in fact, be used as a means of performing useful functions. of individual and social surveillance and control, which represents a new cycle of Foucauldian panopticism, according to his work FOUCAULT, Michel. *Vigilar y castigar*. Nacimiento de la prisión. Mexico: Siglo XXI, 1983. p. 43 et seq.

²² The CAPPs system has been in operation since 1998 and stems from the terrorist attacks during the 1996 Olympic Games in Atlanta, as well as the tragic outcome of TWA Flight 800, which crashed into the Pacific Ocean as a result of *mechanical failure*. More information can be found at: <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-04-385>. Accessed on: April 27, 2024.

alienating digital technology.²³ In addition, a *surveillance capitalism*²⁴ has emerged from AI and social media, with the establishment of large economic monopolies that characterize what has been called *technological feudalism*,²⁵ which can be seen in corporations such as Facebook, Google, Amazon, Apple, Microsoft, Netflix, autocratic rulers, and uncontrolled citizens who have occupied a space that was thought to be collective.²⁶

For this reason, the Digital Markets Act, recently approved by Europe, establishes a set of clearly defined objective criteria for qualifying large *online* platforms as *gatekeepers*,²⁷ aiming to ensure that they behave in a manner that respects individual and social rights and guarantees.²⁸ Despite this, it is in the name of public safety against acts of terrorism and organized crime, several governments have developed programs to monitor their citizens around the world, as Federico Kukso informs us, when he mentions that in China, banks, airports, hotels, and even public restrooms verify people's identities by scanning their faces using *software* called *Xue Liang* (sharp eyes), which analyzes millions of images to track people, detect suspicious behavior, and even predict crimes.²⁹ The author demonstrates government initiatives—either isolated or in global collaboration—to access private and public data and information, from individuals and legal entities, in the name of preventive and curative security, without any information or accountability to those affected by their policies.³⁰

²³ See the interesting article published on *the website*: <https://www.poder360.com.br/poder-tech/tecnologia/leis-rigorosas-garantem-controle-social-na-internet-chinesa/>. Accessed on: April 30, 2024.

²⁴ A topic explored in depth by ZUBOFF, Shoshana. *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism*. New York: Perseus Books, 2019. p. 61 et seq.

²⁵ MOROZOV, Evgeny. *The net delusion: the dark side of internet freedom*. New York: Public Affairs, 2019. p. 38. Along the same lines, see VAROUFAKIS, Yanis. *Technofeudalism*. London: Bodley Head, 2023. For Varoufakis, the big tech companies Meta, Amazon, Apple, and Alphabet control our attention and mediate our transactions, turning humans into digital servants who incessantly post, browse, and buy on their platforms. Instead of pursuing profits derived from labor, the lords of technology, whom he calls *cloudalists*, extract rents.

²⁶ Nowadays, there is already talk of a new market in which it is possible to transfer personal data in exchange for personalized product benefits. In this way, users can consider the possibility of providing their data in exchange for the use of those products (especially when most people provide their data without receiving any compensation for it).

²⁷ Understood as large digital platforms that provide a predefined set of digital services, such as *online* search engines, app stores, and messaging services. These companies have: (i) a strong economic position, with a significant impact on the internal market, operating in several EU countries; (ii) a strong intermediation position, meaning that they connect a large user base to a large number of companies; (iii) a consolidated and lasting position in the market. On September 6, 2023, the European Commission designated Alphabet, Amazon, Apple, ByteDance, Meta, and Microsoft as *gatekeepers*.

²⁸ See news item on *the website*: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/digital-markets-act-ensuring-fair-and-open-digital-markets_en. Accessed on: April 29, 2024.

²⁹ See the article published on *the website*: <https://wtm.inf.br/artigos/170-milhoes-de-cameras-monitoram-possiveis-terroristas-na-china/>. Accessed on: April 30, 2024.

³⁰ KUKSO, Federico. Una historia de control. In: STANCANELLI, Pablo. *El Atlas de la revolución digital – Del sueño libertario al capitalismo de vigilancia*. Buenos Aires: Capital Intelectual, 2019. p. 12. Remember

Let us also remember the digital espionage tool called *Pegasus*, created by the Israeli company NSO Group, used to tap *smartphones*, computers, and communication and data management networks globally, all in the name of promoting the security of democracy and democratic peoples.³¹ Furthermore, these technological resources used by the public (state) and private (market) sectors, because they generally rely on closed-source *software*, make it impossible to achieve levels of transparency and visibility of the neural elements of their operations, thus preventing more effective social, political, and legal controls more effective social, political, and legal controls.³²

Due to these scenarios, it has become increasingly common to talk about the emergence of a surveillance society and a monitored democracy, to the point that some journalists claim that privacy and intimacy are now rights and guarantees that are somewhat outdated, particularly in times of growing global insecurity. This is why there is widespread concern in society about the dynamics of the uncontrollable daily expansion of community surveillance, which has an architecture and logistics unprecedented in the history of civilization. We need only look at the number of surveillance cameras in a wide variety of public and private spaces (stores, banks, public squares, streets, etc.):

author that these systems can also be used to track shady political objectives involving attacks on dissidents or opponents and critics and governments of the day.

³¹ See the excellent article published on *the* Globo companies' *website*: <https://g1.globo.com/economia/tecnologia/noticia/2021/07/19/entenda-o-que-e-o-pegasus-software-de-espionagem-que-teria-sido-usado-para-invadir-smartphones-de-milhares-de-pessoas.ghtml>. Accessed on: April 25, 2023, noting that, once installed, Pegasus allows attackers to access any type of data available on the hacked device, including the use of the microphone and camera, which is why it is sold to various government agencies to collect data on individuals suspected of crimes and terrorism.

³²The FBI in the US has long used a wide variety of closed-source *software* to spy on individuals and organizations in the name of national security, long before the attacks on the Twin Towers in 2001. We need only recall the Omnivore (1991) and Carnivore (1997) programs, which monitored e-mails and electronic communications—later replaced by commercially available *software*. In this regard, see the article by BAMFORD, James. The shadow factory: the ultra-secrets NSA from 9/11 to the eavesdropping on America. *Democracy Now*, Oct. 14, 2008. Available at: https://www.democracynow.org/2008/10/14/james_bamford_the_shadow_factory_the. Accessed on: Apr. 29, 2024.

³³As Scott McNealy, CEO of Sun Microsystems, states in the text *Private Lives? Not ours!* Available at: https://www.pcworld.com/article/16331/private_lives_not_ours.html. Accessed on: May 23, 2022. There is also an excellent critique of these times by VATTIMO, Gianni. *La società trasparente*. Rome: Garzanti, 2000. We address these issues in the book LEAL, Rogerio Gesta and LEAL, Rogerio Gesta; SILVA, Ricardo Machado da. *The fundamental social right to public security in a democratic state governed by the rule of law – Parameters for public policy implementation*. Cruz Alta: Ilustração, 2023.

³⁴ See how some newspapers report on these issues, emphasizing only the positive aspects: "With these solutions, it is possible to create alerts and perform forensic analysis on video, reducing the time needed to conduct an investigation, allowing for automatic notification or searches with filters to identify individuals and vehicles, such as clothing color filters, accessories such as bags and backpacks, object size, direction of movement, vehicle license plate, make, model, among other information. Among the main technologies used in urban monitoring are facial recognition (FR), license plate reading (LPR) technologies

3 Reactions to the surveillance society: perspectives

Despite all these scenarios, society has reacted to panoptic movements such as those mentioned above and clearly defined by Ryan McKinley, a researcher at *the MIT Media Lab*,³⁵ by developing a system called *Government Information Awareness (GIA)*,³⁶ which is presented as a response by citizens to government digital control initiatives.

The GIA initiative is based on a simple rationale: if the government has the right to know personal details about citizens, citizens also have the right to know critical information about their governments. The GIA project has developed user-friendly technologies that allow people to create their own intelligence agencies to obtain, classify, and act on information they gather about their governments, as well as to document matters of public interest, such as information related to campaign financing, the résumés of public officials, documenting the existence of complaints, the secret or confidential relationships of large corporations, information that has been kept classified, and even a profiling system based on the study of patterns.

Along the same lines, we have the creation of so-called *weblogs*.³⁷ Initially, *weblogs* were conceived as structured systems on the internet that allowed anyone to publish personal information, similar to a diary, with the ability to register email addresses, include images, and interact asynchronously. However, they quickly evolved into true digital newspapers, where it is possible to find different points of view on a given event. These tools now compete – in the virtual space – with conventional news media.

As technological change is ecological and not additive, everything is redefined, including old criminal practices, which discover unprecedented opportunities with

and audio detection and classification solutions" (*Jornal Diário do Comércio*, Oct. 5, 2022. Available at: <https://diariodocomercio.com.br/opiniaovideomonitoramento-para-cidades-seguras/>. Accessed on: May 2, 2024).

³⁵ Available at: <https://www.media.mit.edu>. Accessed on: April 27, 2024.

³⁶ See the *website*: <https://www.media.mit.edu/projects/open-government-information-awareness/overview/>. Accessed on: April 27, 2024. See also the interesting *website*: <https://www.wired.com/2003/07/slideshow-government-prying-the-good-kind/>. Accessed on: April 27, 2024.

³⁷ In 1996, Dave Winer implemented a *weblog*, creating the virtual space *24 Hours for Democracy*, an *online* meeting held to support freedom of expression on the internet. Some *techno-celebrities* participated in the innovative event, such as Bill Gates, founder and owner of Microsoft, and Phillippe Kahn, from Novell. Later, Winer himself founded a company specifically dedicated to creating and developing software that would facilitate the creation of *weblogs*. The result of this project was Winer's personal *blog*, one of the world's leading references on the trend (SAUER, Moritz. *Weblogs, podcasting & online-journalism*. Cambridge: O'Reilly Verlag GmbH & Co., 2017). p. 34 et seq.

³⁸ SAUER, Moritz. *Weblogs, podcasting & online journalism*. Cambridge: O'Reilly Verlag GmbH & Co., 2017. p. 29.

the introduction of new information and communication technologies based on AI.³⁹ An example of this is cybercrime, an activity that poses a real threat to the development of the economy (physical and digital) and the information society, which is why the Convention on Cybercrime was established in Budapest on November 23, 2001, signed by numerous countries of the Council of Europe.

The problem is that this document has led to a significant reduction in certain fundamental rights guarantees, including the suggestion that internet access and service providers keep records of their customers' activities in cyberspace (Articles 17, 18, 24, and 25), violating the privacy and other rights of internet users, as well as being contrary to the principles established in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

The institutional structures of states have also been strengthened to tackle these problems, as we can see in Chile, with the creation of *the Cybercrime Investigation Brigade* (BRICIB),⁴² linked to the investigative police; in Mexico, with the *Cyber Police*,⁴³ linked to the Federal Preventive Police; in Spain, with the *Central Technological Investigation Brigade*,⁴⁴ linked to the Spanish Police Directorate General; in Portugal, with the National Unit for Combating Cybercrime and Technological Crime, linked to the Judicial Police; in Brazil, with the Special Unit for Investigating Cybercrimes, linked to the Federal Police.⁴⁵ All these bodies develop internet surveillance policies, with

³⁹ On the regulation of artificial intelligence in the European Union: MIRANZO DÍAZ, Javier. The European Union's Artificial Intelligence Regulation: risk regulation and standardization systems. *A&C – Revista de Direito Administrativo & Constitucional*, Belo Horizonte, year 24, no. 96, pp. 43-78, Apr./Jun. 2024. DOI: 10.21056/aec.v24i96.1932.

⁴⁰ Brazil issued Decree No. 11,941, dated April 12, 2023, enacting the Convention on Cybercrime in the national territory, ratified by the country on March 1, 2023.

⁴¹ It should be noted that Convention No. 108, which is binding on the Member States of the Council of Europe, prohibits in Article 6 the automatic processing of data revealing racial origin, political opinions, religious beliefs, health, or sex life, unless national legislation provides for adequate safeguards. However, Article 9 allows exceptions to protect state security, public safety, the financial interests of the state, the prosecution of criminal offenses, or to protect the rights and freedoms of third parties. It remains to be seen how these issues will be addressed in the new Convention 108+, adopted in 2023, which is expected to enter into force in June 2023.

⁴² Further information is available at: <https://www.pdichile.cl/institución/unidades/cibercripen>. Accessed on: April 29, 2024.

⁴³ Further information is available at: <https://www.ssc.cdmx.gob.mx/organizacion-policial/subsecretaria-de-inteligencia-e-investigacion-policial/policia-cibernetica>. Accessed on: April 29, 2024.

⁴⁴ Further information is available at: https://www.policia.es/_es/tupolicia_conocenos_estructura_dao_cgpoliciajudicial_bcit.php#. Accessed on: April 29, 2024.

⁴⁵ This Unit was recently created on June 28, 2022, as reported on the Brazilian Federal Police website: <https://www.gov.br/mj/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/policia-federal-cria-unidade-especial-para-intensificar-a-repressao-a-crimes-ciberneticos>. Accessed on: April 30, 2024. Brazilian states are also beginning to create specialized units for this purpose, as shown in the news published on December 18, 2020, by the State of São Paulo: <https://www.saopaulo.sp.gov.br/spnoticias/governo-do-estado-inaugura-divisao-de-crimes-ciberneticos-2/>. Accessed on: April 30, 2024. In Rio Grande do Sul, on July 3, 2010, the Cybercrime Police Station (DRCI) had already been created, as announced on the government's official website: <https://ssp.rs.gov.br/policia-civil-gaucha-cria-delegacia-pioneira-em-crimes-virtuais>. Accessed on: April 30, 2024.

focus on the actions of *hackers*, websites, communities, and *chat* rooms where child pornography is promoted (analyzing the activities of local and international pedophile organizations, child prostitution networks, and child trafficking networks that exploit them in other countries), crimes against intellectual property, electronic fraud, money laundering, arms trafficking, human trafficking, and drug trafficking.

In Brazil, we have made progress on these issues, particularly since the enactment of legislation focused on the use of new technologies, namely:

- (i) Law No. 12,258/2010, which amended the Criminal Enforcement Law to promote the possibility of *using surveillance equipment by those convicted by the courts—electronic monitoring—for cases of temporary release in the semi-open regime and serving sentences under house arrest*;
- (ii) Law No. 12,403/2011, which amended the Code of Criminal Procedure and instituted electronic monitoring as a *precautionary measure*, pursuant to Article 319, item IX, of this law;⁴⁶
- (iii) Law No. 12,681/2012, establishing the National System for Public Safety, Prison, *Weapons and Ammunition Traceability, Genetic Material, Fingerprints, and Drugs Information* (SINESP), which uses an integrated information platform from the Federal Government and state databases, with the aim of creating a national information management structure, producing, collecting, systematizing, and making information available for public security;
- (iv) Law No. 12,737/2012, creating the criminal classification of computer crimes, with low penalties of imprisonment from three months to two years;
- (v) Law No. 12,965/2014, which creates the Brazilian Civil Rights Framework for the Internet;
- (vi) Law No. 13,675/2018, regulated by Decree No. 9,489/2018, creating the Unified Public Security System (SUSP), establishing governance policies through *data standardization, technological integration, intelligence, and operational* integration among security agents in the country;
- (vii) Law No. 13,709/2018, General Personal Data Protection Law;⁴⁷

⁴⁶ In this tool, the user is tracked via satellite using an electronic device (bracelet, wristband, or anklet) that works by means of radio frequency and encrypted information about the user's location. The data collected by the system is sent to a server and can be accessed by a terminal connected to the internet. Arguments in favor of this option consider that it would significantly reduce the prison population, as well as decrease public spending on prisoners and social reintegration; while the arguments against it focus on: (i) the possibility of a return to a totalitarian state, in which society itself would be the prison, (ii) the social stigmatization of the person due to the use of monitoring equipment in public, (iii) the violation of the right to intimacy and privacy. In this regard, see the text by GRECO, Rogério. *Human rights, the prison system, and alternatives to imprisonment*. São Paulo: Saraiva, 2011. p. 118.

⁴⁷ FÁCIO, Rafaella Nátaly. Transparency and the right of access in the processing of personal data: considerations on intersections between the General Data Protection Law and the Access to Information Law in Brazil. *Magazine*

(viii) In 2018, the National Council of Justice (CNJ) created the National Prison Monitoring Database (BNMP), a database and electronic system containing the *registration data of individuals imprisoned in the Brazilian prison system*, with the aim of centralizing information and contributing to access to information by judicial and police authorities, assisting criminal justice authorities in the management of documents relating to arrest/detention and release orders issued throughout the national territory, thereby creating a National Prisoner Registry.

The 2018 National Public Security Plan introduced, as strategy No. 8, *video surveillance with biometric facial recognition*, highlighting the ability of computer software to analyze human faces contained in a specific database, using internet connections to catalog individuals by capturing their biometric data extracted by smartphones, computers, and surveillance cameras.⁴⁸ This public policy in Brazil was primarily focused on the surveillance of borders, interstate boundaries, ports, airports, bus stations, and railways.⁴⁹ But now urban public spaces are also being taken over by these mechanisms, as in the case of the *Smart Sampa* video surveillance platform in São Paulo, which is expected to integrate more than 20,000 cameras by 2024 in the capital.⁵⁰ There is much controversy surrounding the project: legal challenges,⁵¹ a suspended public notice, significant resistance from society, and a history of corruption by the company responsible.⁵²

Eurolatinoamericana de Derecho Administrativo, Santa Fe, v. 10, n. 2, e247, Jul./Dec. 2023. DOI 10.14409/redoeda.v10i2.13413.

⁴⁸ In Europe, the European Data Protection Board, responsible for enforcing the General Data Protection Regulation, issued Guideline 05/2022 on the use of this tool, understanding that it represents a disproportionate interference with the rights of data subjects, as it compromises people's expectation of remaining anonymous, contrary to the principles of self-determination and free participation in democratic societies. See the full document at: https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-052022-use-facial-recognition-technology-area_en. Accessed on: Apr. 29, 2024.

⁴⁹ Numerous countries have used these technologies for the following purposes: (i) monitoring compliance with the *lockdown* adopted during the Covid-19 pandemic (China); (ii) behavioral monitoring of people at the 2020 Olympics in Japan, also due to the pandemic; (iii) monitoring of major events (United Kingdom) to identify people wanted by the police. In the US, there are reports of a proposed federal law (2023) that seeks to regulate the matter (*Facial Recognition Act*), restricting the use of biometric facial recognition (Available at: <https://www.congress.gov/bill/117th-congress/house-bill/9061/text?s=1&r=7>). Accessed on: April 29, 2024).

⁵⁰ Among the movements that have gained momentum in the fight against the platform is the campaign *Take My Face Off Your Radar*, launched by more than 50 civil society organizations with the aim of calling for a ban on the use of cameras for public security (Available at: <https://tremeuostodasamira.org.br>). Accessed on: April 22, 2024).

⁵¹ A report published on the *Conjur* legal website on May 17, 2024, states that four Brazilian states have already arrested more than 1,700 people using facial recognition without adequate regulation. See the full article on the website: <https://www.conjur.com.br/2024-mai-17/sem-regulacao-estados-prendem-centenas-utilizando-reconhecimento-facial/>. Accessed on: May 18, 2024.

⁵² The project website states that: "The new platform also facilitates the integration of various municipal services, such as CET, SAMU, Civil Defense, and GCM, into a single platform through the creation of a modern

- (i) Decree No. 10,882/2021, creating the National Public Security Plan – 2021/2030, aiming, among other goals, to promote *technological expansion* in the promotion of public security policies, using standardization, integration, and interoperability of public security data between the Union, states, Federal District, and municipalities (strategy No. 7);⁵³
- (ii) also in 2021, a policy was instituted for *the adoption of body-worn cameras on police uniforms*, installed on police officers' uniforms, helmets, or glasses, with the capacity to capture and record video and audio of the activities carried out by officers in their police routine, such as traffic recordings, arrests, searches, and interrogations.⁵⁴

The problem is that, in general, these virtual public security policies are structured around closed-source *software* tools, which has increased social and political pressure globally to regulate *big tech*, as well as expanding the use of open-source systems, some of which are already part of *the Software Choice Initiative*, which has made progress in this regard, including: Intel (USA), Linux (USA), Open Solutions (Argentina), Paradigma (Brazil), Peruvian Software Association (Peru), Siam Commercial Bank (Thailand), and VSI (Germany).⁵⁵ These open models would at least provide greater guarantees

Integrated Monitoring Center. In addition, with the new cameras, security agencies will be able to monitor schools, UBS, and other public facilities, significantly increasing security in these locations. The technical cameras will also feature heat monitoring, facilitating supervision in squares and parks, which usually have trees and green areas that can hinder more accurate surveillance” (Available at: <https://participemais.prefeitura.sp.gov.br/legislation/processes/209>. Accessed on: Apr. 22, 2024).

⁵³ Available at: https://www.gov.br/mj/pt-br/centrais-de-contenido/publicacoes/categorias-de-publicacoes/planos/plano_nac_de_seguranca_publica_e_def_soc_2021__2030.pdf. Accessed on: April 29, 2024.

⁵⁴The state of São Paulo was a pioneer in adopting this practice, which has been replicated in other states such as Rio de Janeiro, Minas Gerais, Pará, Santa Catarina, and Rio Grande do Sul. See the article by the Center for the Study of Violence at the University of São Paulo on *the website*: <https://nev.prp.usp.br/projetos/pesquisa-uso-cameras-corporais-pela-policia-militar-de-sp/>. Accessed on: April 29, 2024. The *website* reports that, in the state of São Paulo: “A study conducted by the Brazilian Forum on Public Safety indicated an overall 62.7% drop in police lethality between 2019 and 2022, with special emphasis on units already equipped with COPs. An analysis conducted by CCAS/FGV, in collaboration with PMESP, indicates that the cameras were directly responsible for a 57% reduction in the number of deaths resulting from police intervention and a 63% drop in bodily injuries caused by military police officers. A recent study by the Sou da Paz Institute reveals that cases of deaths among young people (aged 15 to 24) fell by 46% after the implementation of the cameras.

⁵⁵ See the *website*: <https://web.archive.org/web/20061107202717/http://www.softwarechoice.org/>. Accessed on: April 29, 2024. In the United Kingdom, on July 15, 2002, the *Commerce Office* launched the open source *software* project. This initiative affirms that well-configured open source *software* can be as secure as proprietary systems and is currently subject to fewer attacks over the internet. For this reason, a balance must be struck between the availability of administration and security skills and the advantages that different systems can provide. See the information on *the website*: https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a79cceed915d042206b200/All_About_Open_Source_v2_0.doc&ved=2ahUKEwiY6LC4vueFAxVqrpUCHVqmDL8QFnoEEDAQAQ&usq=AOvVaw1q_eK5Ym0tvDSO4c8dUjw2. Accessed on: April 29, 2024.

monitoring and visibility techniques for data access and management processes, both for individuals and the State.⁵⁶

In terms of the judicialization of these discussions, it is worth remembering the decisions of the Federal Supreme Court (STF) in Declaratory Action of Unconstitutionality No. 6,649 and Action for Non-Compliance with Fundamental Precept No. 695, which held that the sharing of personal data between public agencies—even for public security purposes—presupposes legitimate and specific purposes,⁵⁷ and the procedure must comply with all the requirements of the General Data Protection Law (Law No. 13,709/2018).⁵⁸ If the LGPD guidelines are not followed, the State will be objectively liable for damages caused to individuals. And any civil servant who intentionally violates the duty of disclosure established in Article 23, I, of the LGPD will be liable for administrative impropriety.

Similarly, in Case No. 977,⁶⁰ the STF is tackling the thorny issue of whether access to telephone records, contact lists, and other data contained in cell phones seized at the scene of a crime attributed to the accused requires a prior court decision that justifies, based on concrete evidence, the necessity and appropriateness of the measure, and limits its scope in light of the fundamental rights to privacy⁶¹ and the confidentiality of individuals' communications and data.

4 Concluding notes

We therefore conclude from these reflections that certain premises are important for enabling democratic public security policies with the use of virtual technologies, namely:

⁵⁶Regarding the fundamental right to data protection, see: ARAÚJO, Valter Shuenquener de; PERIM, Maria Clara Mendonça; RIBEIRO, Koryander Figueirêdo. The asymmetries of state regulation for the protection of personal data and the affirmation of fundamental rights of the first dimension. *A&C – Revista de Direito Administrativo & Constitucional*, Belo Horizonte, year 22, no. 87, pp. 267-296, Jan./Mar. 2022. DOI: 10.21056/aec.v22i87.1453; SÁNCHEZ DÍAZ, María Fernanda. The right to personal data protection in the digital age. *Euro-Latin American Journal of Administrative Law*, Santa Fe, vol. 10, no. 1, e235, Jan./June 2023. DOI: 10.14409/reodoeda.v10i1.12626.

⁵⁷ On the jurisprudence of the Federal Supreme Court on data communication: ABREU, Jacqueline de Souza. Communication of data, not data itself: origins and problems of the current paradigm of constitutional protection of data confidentiality. *Revista de Investigações Constitucionais*, Curitiba, v. 11, no. 1, e256, Jan./Apr. 2024. DOI: 10.5380/rinc.v11i1.89280.

⁵⁸ MARTINS, Ricardo Marcondes. Data protection, powers of federal entities, and Constitutional Amendment No. 115/22. *Journal of Constitutional Research*, Curitiba, v. 9, no. 3, p. 645-658, Sept./Dec. 2022. DOI: 10.5380/rinc.v9i3.87107.

⁵⁹ According to the decision published on the STF website: <https://portal.stf.jus.br/processos/detalhe.asp?incidente=6079238>. Accessed on: Apr. 30, 2024.

⁶⁰ According to the STF website: https://jurisprudencia.stf.jus.br/pages/search?classeNumerolncidente=%22ARE%201042075%22&base=acordaos&sinonimo=true&plural=true&page=1&pageSize=10&sort=_score&sortBy=desc&isAdvanced=true. Accessed on: April 30, 2024.

⁶¹ ROBLES OSOLLO, Ana Gloria. The right to privacy and the protection of cross-border personal data. *Euro-Latin American Journal of Administrative Law*, Santa Fe, v. 8, n. 1, p. 35-60, Jan. /June 2021. DOI 10.14409/reodoeda.v8i1.9543.

- a) Legal and regulatory frameworks: with the application and harmonization of current legal and regulatory frameworks to promote an environment of certainty and confidence in the adoption, use, and promotion of technologies.
- b) Interoperability: around the structural, technical, organizational, and governance capabilities needed to share information and generate knowledge, with transparency and public accountability;
- c) open data: making government information available in formats that are useful and reusable by different government entities, the public, civil society organizations, cooperatives, and universities, among others, to promote entrepreneurship and governance based on the idea of citizen security;
- d) connectivity and appropriate digital tools: strengthening and developing networks (governmental and citizen), expanding better infrastructure in the territories and the capacity of existing networks, and developing (i) skills in the technology sector to stimulate applications mainly in massive cellular networks, and (ii) virtual tools that enable applications for complaints/demands/responses on multiple platforms;⁶²
- e) citizen participation and digital skills: equitable development of skills to develop and operate digital technologies and services, including social coverage and skills development in community systems;
- f) digital communication and social networks: as a tool for training and social awareness to support digital strategies, digital communication focused on citizens and their needs as consumers of security and coexistence, providing services based on knowledge management, and not just information.

In Brazil in particular, these elements are not yet fully present, which will require a lot of time.

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⁶²Venezuela has an app called *Patrulha Inteligente* (Smart Patrol), which detects the security quadrant corresponding to the user's location, provided by their cell phone's GPS or through their network provider, and provides information so that they can contact the associated emergency phone number. Citizens can call the police and military authorities closest to their area and make their complaints anonymously. More information on *the website*: <https://consejogeneraldepolicia.org/opinion/patrullaje-inteligente/>. Accessed on: Apr. 29, 2024.

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Additional information

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